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ASSESSMENT OF HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS HAVING CARDIO VASCULAR DISEASES (CVD) ATTENDING DIFFERENT HOSPITALS IN QUETTA PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVE: A cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the leading cause of mortality in the world especially in developing countries. The primary objective of this study was to determine the quality of life in CVD patients living in Quetta, Pakistan and to provide better health to these patients in future. **METHODS AND DESIGN:** A cross-sectional, questionnaire based survey was conducted in March 2016 to September 2016. Total 227 patients participated from different tertiary care hospitals in this study. Convenience sampling was applied due to short period of time. All the collected information was summarized through SPSS and then analyzes it manually. **RESULTS:** Research shows poor quality of life among CVD patients. Different articles were studied for this purpose. Total of 227 patients QoL was studied using MLHFQ instrument. Factors like age, sex, qualification, mostly affect the QoL. MLHFQ contains three different categories among which physical and emotional factors have worst impact on QoL. **CONCLUSION:** The result of the study shows poor quality of life of cardio vascular patients. In addition to CVD if people have some other chronic diseases then HRQoL of them is further lowering. For better QoL among these patient's health programmers must be conducting to improve their QoL.

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INTRODUCTION

Quality of life (QoL) describes happiness and satisfactory life of an individual, but the main factor is health, so a person have good quality of life if he has health [1]. In 1990's different questionnaires were formed to measure quality of life [2]. QoL can be measure by an individual level to their personal expectations [3]. We need to get information about individual health that how chronic diseases effect their life so researchers will help to improve quality of life. An individual health is depending upon QoL so disorders in the quality direct or indirect effect the health. Indirect effects include social life of a person. While direct effect include diseases that hospitalized the patient or may even lead a patient towards death [4]. Cardio vascular diseases is the most chronic diseases that causes high rate of mortality and disability in the world. It is the leading cause of the death in the world especially in the developing countries [5]. Causes of CVD include Hypertension, Atherosclerosis, Plaque, Circulatory shock, Thrombus, Embolism, Stroke, Heart attack, Angina pectoris, Congestive heart failure, Aneurysm, Dissolving blood clots [6]. There are some factors on which CVD depend among which Hypertension (high blood pressure), Tobacco use, Raised blood glucose (diabetes), Physical inactivity, Unhealthy diet, Cholesterol/lipids, Overweight and obesity are modifiable risk factors [7]. Non modifiable risk factor includes age, sex and family history. about 7.3 millions deaths are caused by CVD among which 80% people are from developing countries [5] from which 90% are caused by modifiable risk factors.

METHODOLOGY

Quality of life in cardio vascular patient can be measured by interviewing or questionnaire based method.

STUDY DESIGN:

This research was designed as questionnaire based, cross sectional study

STUDY DESIGN:

The cross-sectional questionnaire based study was conducted in different hospitals of Quetta Pakistan.

STUDY SETTINGS:

The study was conducted in different Government and Private hospitals of Quetta Pakistan, Including Sandeman provincial hospital Quetta, Bolan medical complex (government hospitals) and from Heart and General hospital Quetta.

STUDY DURATION:

The study was conducted from March 2016 to September 2016.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

The study has adopted convenient sampling technique to fill questionnaire from the study sample.

SAMPLE SIZE:

no convenient method was adopted in a given time 227 sample was collected.

STUDY TOOL:

Minnesota living with heart failure questionnaire (MLHFQ) was selected as an instrument tool. It is consist of 21 different questions with 6 options from no-very much. First portion is of demographics and second portion contains questions. Among these 21 questions 8 (Q#2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 12, 13) were in physical factors, 5 questions were in emotional factor (Q# 17, 18, 19, 20, 21), and 8 questions were in others (Q#1, 8, 9, 10, 11, 14, 15, 16).

DATA COLLECTION:

Convenient sampling was done under limited resources and limited time. Questionnaires were distributed along with the consent form among the patients who were educated and interview the uneducated patient for filling questionnaire.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Coded data was entered in SPSS (IBM) version 20. Descriptive statistics were used to demonstrate the characteristics of the study population. variables were measured as frequency, percentages mean \pm standard deviation. Inferential statistics used to assess the significance among study variables.

SCORING:

Scoring was done by summing the responses to all 21 questions. In addition, a physical dimension score (items 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 12, 13 on the version sent with these instructions) and emotional dimension score (items 17, 18, 19, 20, 21) have been identified by factor analysis and may be scored by simple summation to further characterize the effect of heart failure on a patient's life. Each question have 6 option. Circle either the 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 to indicate how much the question affected your life during the past month – zero (0) means not at all, one (1) means very little and five (5) very much.

Ethical consideration:

Ethical Standards of Human Experimentation of the national Bioethics Committee [8] were followed during the study & care was taken as not to violate any of the standard set forth by the committee. Participants were assured of their Privacy. Patients were informed both verbally & in writing about the Aim of the study, the Risks & benefits, and their rights of participation. Their Consent was taken in form of a signature at the consent form & they were assured of their privacy the permission was taken from the Minnesota university, their tools using license agreement etc, for collecting data information permission is taken from MS of different hospitals.

RESULT:

The result shows worst quality of life among the patients having CVD.

DEMOGRAPHICS:

Table 1 shows the demographics details of respondents. A total of 207 respondents were included in the current study, out of which (103)49% were males and (104) 50.2% were females. The respondents age was 30-89 from which most of the affected people aged 45-70. Among 207 people 168 (81.2%) were married and 39 (18.8%) were unmarried. Most of the peoples were illiterate having frequency 107 (51.7%). 74 (38.8%) were lived in rural areas while 135 (65.2%) were lived in urban area.

TABLE# 1:

Description	Response N	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	103	49.8%
	Female	104	50.2%
Age	30-39	22	10.6%
	40-49	49	23.7%
	50-59	49	23.7%
	60-69	45	21.7%
	70-79	30	14.5%
	80-89	11	5.3%
Marital status	Married	168	81.2%
	Unmarried	39	18.8%
Qualification	None	107	51.7%
	Primary	21	10.1%
	Middle	18	8.7%
	Secondary	22	10.6%
	Inter	16	7.7%
	Bachelors	14	6.8%
	Masters	6	2.9%
	Others	3	1.8%
Locality	Rural(Village)	72	34.8%
	Urban (City)	135	65.2%

QUESTION RESPONSE:**PHYSICAL RESPONSE:**

According to (table2) 8 physical factors were included in this category. In question#2 maximum respondents were given to (4) much i.e. 68(32.9%) .In question# 3 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 69(33.3%). In question#4 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 63(30.4%).. In question#5 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 50(24.2%). In question#6 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 49(23.7%). In question#7 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 60(29.0%). In question#12 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 56(27.1%). In question#13 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 66(31.9%). according to the collected data most of the people have short of breath have difficulty in doing household work, climbing stairs. They have to rest during day.

TABLE#2: Physical Factors.

Question	0 (no)	1(very little)	2(little)	3(moderate)	4(much)	5(very much)
Making your sit or lay down to rest during day difficult?	5(2.4%)	12(5.8%)	35(16.9%)	23(11.1%)	68(32.9%)	64(30.9%)
Making your walking or climbing difficult?	15(7.2%)	9(4.3%)	11(5.3%)	39(18.8%)	69(33.3%)	64(30.9%)
Making your working around the house or yard difficult?	24(11.6%)	9(4.3%)	30(14.9%)	27(13%)	63(30.4%)	54(26.1%)
Making your going places away from home difficult?	21(10.1%)	14(6.8%)	37(17.9%)	39(18.8%)	50(24.2%)	46(22.2%)
Making your sleep will at night difficult?	25(12.1%)	24(11.6%)	32(15.5%)	34(16.4%)	49(23.7%)	43(20.8%)
Making your relating or doing things with your friends and family difficult?	15(7.2%)	12(5.8%)	34(16.4%)	28(13.5%)	60(29%)	58(28%)
Making you short of breath?	14(6.8%)	13(6.3%)	53(25.6%)	35(16.9%)	56(27.1%)	36(17.4%)
Making you tired, fatigue and low on energy?	8(3.9%)	4(1.9%)	20(9.7%)	45(21.7%)	66(31.9%)	63(30.4%)

EMOTIONAL FACTORS:

According to table#3, 5 questions were there (Q# 17,18,19,20,21). In question#17 maximum respondents were given to (5) very much i.e. 44(21.3%). In question#18 the maximum people give response to (2) little i.e. 46(22.2%). In question#19 maximum respondents were given to (5) very much i.e. 53(25.6%). In question#20 the maximum people responded to (5) very much i.e. 52(25.1%), In question#21 the maximum people responded to (5) very much i.e. 70(33.8%). According to result most of the people were depressed, worry, and did not remember things. Few of people think that they are burden to their family

TABLE#3: Emotional Factors.

Question	0 (no)	1(very little)	2(little)	3(moderate)	4(much)	5(very much)
Making you feel you are a burden to your family and friends?	38(18.4%)	20(9.7%)	33(15.9%)	43(20.3%)	28(13.5%)	44(21.3%)
Making you feel a loss of self control in a life?	26(12.6%)	17(8.2%)	46(22.2%)	30(14.5%)	44(21.3%)	44(21.3%)
Make you worry?	18(8.7%)	18(8.7%)	35(16.9%)	35(16.9%)	48(23.2%)	53(25.6%)
Making it difficult for you to concentrate or remember things?	20(9.7%)	15(7.2%)	44(21.3%)	13(16.9%)	40(19.3%)	52(25.1%)
Making you feel depressed?	18(8.7%)	7(3.4%)	36(17.4%)	32(15.5%)	44(21.3%)	70(33.8%)

According to table#4, In question#1 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 78(37.7%). In question#8 the maximum people responded to (0) no i.e. 68(32.9%). In question#9 the maximum people responded to (3) moderate i.e. 45(21.7%). In question#10 the maximum people responded to (0) no i.e. 70(33.8%). In question#11 the maximum people responded to (5) very much i.e. 93(44.9%). In question#14 the maximum people responded to (4) much i.e. 66(31.9%). In question#15 the maximum people responded to (5) very much i.e. 77(37.2%). In question#16 the maximum people responded to (2) little i.e. 50(24.2%). Most of the people found it to be a costly disease they have to stay longer in a hospital, having side effects from treatment. In earning this result shows negative impact as most of the females have CVD and in Pakistan most of the females do house hold jobs.

TABLE#4: Others.

Question	0 (no)	1(very little)	2(little)	3(moderate)	4(much)	5(very much)
Causing swelling in your ankles or legs?	13(6.3%)	10(4.8%)	39(18.8%)	26(12.6%)	78(37.7%)	41(19.8%)
Making your working to earn a living difficult?	68(32.9%)	18(8.7%)	43(20.8%)	24(11.6%)	25(12.1%)	29(14%)
Making your recreational, past times, sports or hobbies difficult?	29(14%)	11(5.3%)	40(19.3%)	45(21.7%)	37(17.9%)	44(21.3%)
Making your sexual activities difficult?	70(33.8%)	11(5.3%)	30(14.5%)	25(12.1%)	47(22.7%)	24(11.6%)
Making you eat less of the food you like?	7(3.4%)	7(3.4%)	20(9.7%)	27(30.0%)	53(25.6%)	93(44.9%)
Making you stay in a hospital?	16(7.7%)	22(10.6%)	53(25.6%)	37(17.9%)	66(31.9%)	63(30.4%)
Costing you money for medical care?	14(6.8%)	13(6.3%)	20(9.7%)	37(17.9%)	46(22.2%)	77(37.2%)
Giving you side effects from treatment?	13(6.3%)	20(9.7%)	50(24.2%)	35(16.9%)	41(19.8%)	48(23.2%)

DISCUSSION

In Quetta Pakistan people have worst quality of life according to the data collected through MLHF questionnaire. Emotional factors and social factors mostly effected the the life of these patients. The questionnaire filled by the patients shows similarity in how cvd effects the life of people. Mostly people have too much difficulty in climbing stairs, in walking, in doing things. The physical factors badly effects the health of people. In developing countries CVD is the leading cause of mortality in the world. According to dawn news in Pakistan 38% of all the deaths is caused by CVD [9]. In 2014 the death rate due to CVD reaches to the 111,367 i.e 10% of the total deaths. Due to which Pakistan is at #63 in the world.[10]. This research is conducting for checking QoL in patients having cardiovascular diseases in Quetta Pakistan. People of Pakistan contain too much fats in their diet which leads towards hypertension, heart failure, atherosclerosis etc which is the leading cause of CVD. Research shows most of the people affected with CVD belong to the age of 45-70. In developing countries mostly 68 is the average age in which CVD effects the people [11].

CONCLUSION

This research shows that Pakistani people have poor quality of life regarding cardio vascular diseases. It effects a high population more researches will help to improve the life in the future. These results indicate that CVD complications are associated with worse health-related quality of life of Quetta citizen. Finally, we found that the MLHFQ is a reasonably good. The subject of CVD is a comorbid disease that frequently confounds with diabetes, hypertension, cholesterol, lack of physical activities etc adding significantly to its overall morbidity and mortality. CVD have poorer HRQoL in all domains with significantly lower scores on MLHF social functioning, emotional and physical role.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Our results showed poor quality of life among the patients, this data is helpful in clinical practice, especially in the early treatment of CVD, at which point improvement and self-management of HRQoL is still possible. We found that CVD have a negative impact on HRQoL . These data not only helps in clinical disease management, but also in education and improving HRQoL. Further research on appropriate interventions aimed at HRQoL of these participants is needed. Cost effective, appropriate and publicly available preventive strategies are required for controlling the situation and prevention of CVD in Pakistan. Coordinated and efforts are needed both from governmental and non-governmental organizations to make a plans to overcome the mortality rate due these CVD.

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